

Part of
TeleRehaB DSS Data Management Plan

Description

TeleRehaB DSS Data Management Plan_RCT_Data

Description

The purpose of this data collection is to assess the acceptability and feasibility of a home-based balance tele-rehabilitation program for older adults, particularly those at risk of falls. This data generation is closely tied to the project's objectives, as it directly informs the development of a scalable, accessible, and effective digital solution that can improve patient outcomes through targeted interventions tailored to specific health conditions affecting balance and fall risk. The project aims to address fall prevention and rehabilitation needs for patients with multiple risk factors, leveraging innovative digital health technology to deliver therapy remotely.

Researchers

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TeleRehabilitation of Balance
clinical and economic Decision
Support System
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Description

1 Summary

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Research Data

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

New

The dataset described in the TeleRehaB DSS project consists of **primary data**, as it involves newly collected information that has not undergone prior processing or analysis. The data collection process is directly tied to the project's clinical study, which generates original data through participant assessments, sensor recordings, questionnaires, and other evaluations. This primary data includes demographic details, clinical assessments, system usability feedback, and sensor-based activity data, all collected for the first time during the study.

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Observational

During randomized control trials (RCTs), data will be collected through clinical assessments, wearable sensor data, participant responses to questionnaires, and treatment adherence logs, as well as participant interactions with the tele-rehabilitation system.

1.1.5 What is its format?

The TeleRehaB DSS project will use various data formats during randomized control trials. **JSON** is used for structured data, such as metadata and sensor outputs. **CSV** and **XLSX** are used for tabular data, such as clinical assessments and questionnaire responses.

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

120-130 MB per participant

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

- To obtain information
- To keep on record

- To make informed decisions
- To improve a product
- To combine with other data

The project aims to gather clinical data, sensor measurements, and participant feedback to assess the effectiveness and feasibility of tele-rehabilitation programs for older adults with falls or balance disorders. The TeleRehaB DSS system will be designed and validated using real-world data from randomized controlled trials. The system will be refined and optimized based on participant feedback and performance outcomes. The data will be integrated with previous projects like HOLOBALANCE for comprehensive analysis and improved predictive modeling. A detailed record will be maintained for long-term analysis and regulatory compliance.

1.1.8 What is its origin / provenance?

The TeleRehaB DSS project's dataset is derived from randomized controlled trials across five international sites. The participating sites include the **University College London (UCL)** in the UK, which focuses on stroke, MCI, and long Covid-19, recruiting 50 participants for both the intervention and control groups. The **National and Kapodistrian University of Athens (NKUA)** in Greece addresses vestibular dysfunction and MCI, enrolling 50 participants in each group. The **University Medical Centre Freiburg (UKLFR)** in Germany also concentrates on stroke, MCI, and long Covid-19, recruiting 50 participants per group. **King Chulalongkorn Memorial Hospital (KMCH) in Thailand** includes participants with stroke, MCI, and vestibular dysfunction, enrolling 30 participants in each group. Finally, the **Secretaria Regional de Saúde e Proteção Civil da Região Autónoma da Madeira (SRS, Madeira)** in Portugal focuses on stroke, vestibular dysfunction, and long Covid-19, with 50 participants in both intervention and control groups.

Overall, the study involves **230 participants** in the intervention group and an equal number of matched controls, resulting in a total sample size of **460**

participants. Each site follows a standardized protocol for participant recruitment, data collection, and assessment to ensure consistency and comparability across centers. The dataset includes diverse populations, allowing for the evaluation of the TeleRehaB DSS's effectiveness across different healthcare settings and demographic groups.

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Research communities
- Decision makers
- Economy

The TeleRehaB DSS project will collect data on rehabilitation and digital health, enabling researchers to evaluate the efficacy of tele-rehabilitation interventions for conditions like stroke, MCI, vestibular disorders, and Covid-19. Clinical researchers can understand patient recovery trajectories and the cognitive and functional impacts of remote rehabilitation programs. Data scientists and AI developers can use sensor-based data to create predictive models for fall risks, treatment adherence, and personalized rehabilitation strategies. The dataset also holds value for healthcare research communities, evaluating feasibility, usability, and scalability in diverse populations and geographic locations. Decision-makers can use the data to optimize treatment protocols, improve patient outcomes, and allocate healthcare resources.

2 Links Between Outputs

2.1 Publications

2.1.1 Does the described output support any scientific publication?

No

2.1.2 Is there a data availability statement provided along with the publication?

No

2.3 Software

2.3.1 Does the described output use or support any software?

No

3 FAIR Practices

3.1 Making data and other outputs findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

Data identifiers

DOI

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

Yes

CERIF (Common European Research Information Format)

3.1.1.3 What type(s) of metadata?

Descriptive

3.1.1.4 Do the metadata use standardised vocabularies?

Yes

3.1.1.6 Are the metadata searchable?

Yes

3.1.1.7 How are searchable metadata provided?

Registry/Catalogue

The TeleRehaB DSS project will utilize a combination of tools and systems to manage and provide access to its metadata and datasets, ensuring compliance

with FAIR principles. The project will use a Registry/Catalogue through Zenodo, which assigns Digital Object Identifiers (DOIs) to datasets, enabling their discoverability and accessibility through academic indexing services and search engines.

3.1.1.8 Are keywords provided in the metadata?

Yes

Clinical data

3.1.1.9 Are metadata harvestable?

No

OAI-PMH protocol

3.2 Making data and other outputs openly accessible

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

Zenodo

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14265573>

Zenodo is a trusted platform developed under the European OpenAIRE program and operated by CERN. It supports the long-term preservation and sharing of datasets and research outputs and assigns DOIs to ensure findability and citation.

3.2.1.2 Is the selected repository a trusted source?

No

3.2.1.5 Does the repository(ies) assign datasets / outputs with persistent identifiers?

Yes

3.2.1.6 Does the repository(ies) resolve the identifiers to a digital object?

When a dataset is assigned a Digital Object Identifier (DOI) by Zenodo, the DOI can be used to directly access the digital object (e.g., dataset, publication, or related research output) via the web.

3.2.1.7 Does the repository support versioning?

Yes

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.1 What is the described dataset / output title?

TeleRehaB RCT Dataset

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Shared

The datasets and outputs from the TeleRehaB DSS project will be shared under clearly defined access modes to ensure compliance with legal, ethical, and contractual obligations while promoting open science where possible. Fully anonymized datasets and metadata will be shared openly via Zenodo, an openaccess repository, ensuring broad accessibility. These datasets will be assigned Digital Object Identifiers (DOIs) for discoverability and reusability and will be made available under Creative Commons licenses. For datasets containing sensitive personal information or proprietary data, restricted access conditions will be applied. These datasets will be only accessible to authorized researchers or institutions through a formal request process and under strict data-sharing agreements. This ensures compliance with GDPR and other relevant regulations governing the use and transfer of sensitive data. Access will be granted via secure, encrypted channels to maintain data confidentiality and integrity. Certain datasets remain closed due to legal, ethical, or contractual constraints. Datasets that cannot be fully anonymized are withheld to comply with GDPR and protect participant privacy. Additionally, data may will be closed due to ethical concerns, such as the risk of participant re-identification, or to protect the legitimate interests of project beneficiaries,

including intellectual property or competitive advantages. Open datasets are published in Zenodo, which ensures long-term preservation and accessibility.

3.2.2.3 What is the reason of limiting access to the dataset / output?

The TeleRehaB DSS project has restricted access to certain datasets or outputs due to legal, ethical, and contractual reasons. GDPR mandates restricted access to sensitive personal information, ensuring participant privacy and confidentiality. Ethical considerations are crucial, especially when data involves vulnerable populations or older adults with cognitive impairments. Contractual obligations arise from data-sharing agreements with clinical partners or thirdparty providers, which may impose conditions on the use or redistribution of proprietary or licensed data. Project beneficiaries may restrict access to protect their intellectual property or proprietary methodologies.

Highsensitivity datasets, such as raw sensor data or detailed clinical information, may also be restricted to prevent misuse or misinterpretation. To address these constraints, the project uses a structured approach to data sharing, with fully anonymized datasets openly shared via the Zenodo repository under Creative Commons licenses. For datasets requiring restricted access, only authorized parties can access the data under strict data-sharing agreements. This balances advancing open science with safeguarding participant privacy and the legitimate interests of all stakeholders involved.

3.2.2.8 Is the described dataset / output supported by a data access committee?

No

3.2.2.9 Please specify how the dataset / output will be accessed during and after the project ends

During the project, the dataset will be restricted to authorized consortium members involved in data processing, analysis, and model development. Access will be granted on a role-based basis, ensuring individuals access only the subset of data required for their specific tasks. The data will be hosted on a

secure, encrypted platform compliant with ISO 27001 or equivalent standards, requiring strong authentication mechanisms like multi-factor authentication (MFA) to prevent unauthorized entry.

The dataset will be used for cleaning and preprocessing, feature extraction and statistical analysis, and model training and validation. Logging and monitoring will be in place to maintain an audit trail, capturing user identity, data accessed, and purpose.

After the project, the dataset will be securely archived in encrypted environments for the legally required retention period. External researchers may request access by submitting a formal application to the Data Management Board (DMB), including the research purpose, data required, and evidence of ethical and legal compliance. Approved external access will be governed by strict licensing agreements, and anonymized datasets may be deposited in trusted repositories for broader reuse under open science principles.

Identity verification during and after the project involves a secure login with multi-factor authentication (MFA) and a formal authorization process. Access permissions will align with the user's role, and access will be monitored and updated as needed. Access monitoring and auditing will ensure compliance with ethical and security standards.

3.2.2.10 Please specify how long after the project has ended the dataset / output will be made accessible for

The dataset/output from the TeleRehaB DSS project will be made accessible for 2 years after the project has ended.

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.1 Will you provide metadata even if the described dataset / output can not be openly shared?

Yes

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.2.3.3 Do metadata provide information about how to access the described dataset / output?

No

3.2.3.4 Will metadata remain available after the dataset / output is no longer available?

No

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

No

3.3.3 Have you applied a standard schema for your (meta)data?

No

3.3.5 What is the methodology followed?

The methodology followed for making data and other outputs interoperable in the TeleRehaB DSS project focuses on ensuring compatibility, usability, and effective integration of data across various platforms and tools, despite not applying a controlled vocabulary or a standard metadata schema. Data is stored and shared in widely recognized, non-proprietary formats such as CSV, JSON and XLSX, facilitating compatibility with diverse software tools. Data collection protocols are standardized across study sites, ensuring consistent definitions and structures for variables to harmonize the data and make it interoperable within the project.

While formal metadata schemas are not applied, metadata is structured to be machine-readable, with key attributes such as dataset titles, descriptions, authors, and file formats consistently included to enable discovery and reuse. The dataset is designed to be interoperable with analytical and modeling tools commonly used in healthcare and rehabilitation research.

The project aligns with the FAIR principles to enhance interoperability. Datasets are assigned persistent identifiers such as DOIs to ensure they are findable, and data is deposited in trusted repositories like Zenodo, making it accessible under

clear protocols. Structured and non-proprietary formats ensure data can be integrated across systems, and comprehensive documentation supports reusability. Internal guidelines for naming conventions, data organization, and version control further ensure consistency across sites and teams. This methodology enables the project outputs to remain interoperable and useful for various research applications, balancing practical needs with flexibility despite the absence of formal controlled vocabularies or metadata schemas.

3.3.6 What community-endorsed interoperability best practices are followed?

The TeleRehaB DSS project adopts several community-endorsed best practices to ensure data and outputs are interoperable, adhering to standards that facilitate sharing, integration, and reuse across various research disciplines and platforms.

3.3.7 Does the described dataset / output provide qualified references with other outputs?

No

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.1 What internationally recognised licence will you use for your dataset / output?

CC0 1.0

3.4.2 What reusability and / or reproducibility methods are followed?

- Codebooks
- Data cleaning
- Analyses

3.4.3 Will you provide the described dataset / output in the public domain?

No

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

Yes

The TeleRehaB DSS project intends to ensure the reuse of its datasets by third parties after the project concludes. A curated subset of the anonymized dataset will be made available to the broader research community under open science principles, balancing the promotion of scientific collaboration with the protection of participant confidentiality and the consortium's intellectual contributions. To achieve this, a carefully selected subset of the dataset, containing no personal or sensitive information, will be shared via the Zenodo repository. This ensures long-term storage and accessibility under secure and well-documented conditions. These datasets will be assigned Digital Object Identifiers (DOIs) to enhance discoverability and proper attribution to the project and its contributors. Licensing terms, will govern data usage, ensuring proper acknowledgment of the project while protecting against unauthorized sharing or re-identification of participants. To respect the intellectual contributions of the consortium, an embargo period will be implemented during which external researchers will not be permitted to publish findings using the shared data. This allows consortium members adequate time to publish their primary findings. Once the embargo period ends, external researchers can access the data subset by complying with the licensing terms and submitting applications reviewed by the Data Management Board (DMB). The DMB will oversee data sharing and monitor usage to ensure compliance with licensing terms. Violations will result in penalties, including revocation of access and reporting to relevant ethical bodies. This framework ensures the TeleRehaB DSS dataset contributes to advancing scientific knowledge while maintaining high standards for data security, ethical compliance, and participant confidentiality.

3.4.5 Is provenance well documented?

Yes

3.4.6 What documented procedures for quality assurance do you have in place?

- Set up of scientific and technical committee
- Data conform to format specification
- Consistency verified with data models and standards

4 Allocation of Resources

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

minor

Euro

- Storage
- Archiving
- Security

Direct cost

Equipment purchase costs and staff costs for preparing the data to be deposited will be covered by the project. Thus, costs are minor since they include only server

maintenance costs or zero in case data are uploaded in Zenodo.

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

Infrastructure Grant

4.1.3 Identify the people who will be responsible and their role(s) in the management of the described output

- a. Dimitrios Fotiadis (0000-0002-7362-5082)
- b. George Matsopoulos (0000-0002-2600-9914)
- c. Doris-Eva Bamiou (0000-0001-7486-4264)

5 Security

5.1 Data Security

5.1.1 What security measures are followed?

Encryption

The TeleRehaB DSS project uses encryption as a primary security measure to protect data during storage and transmission.

5.1.2 What conditions do the security measures meet?

- Data access
- Data storage
- Data transmission
- Data recovery
- Data sharing

The security measures for data security include confidentiality, integrity, availability, and compliance with GDPR and Regulatory Standards. Encryption is used for storage and transmission, safeguarding sensitive information. Backups and monitored data centers ensure data is accessible and recoverable. These measures align with GDPR standards, ensuring compliance with European Union data privacy regulations, especially for personal and health-related data.

5.1.3 How will you preserve the described dataset / output in the long term?

The TeleRehaB DSS project will store its datasets and outputs in the Zenodo repository for long-term preservation. The repository offers persistent identifiers (DOIs) for each dataset, robust data redundancy using CERN's high-capacity storage infrastructure, and adheres to data repository standards for long-term preservation and interoperability. Open access to anonymized and aggregated data ensures data reuse by the broader research community, supporting the sustainability and scientific impact of the data generated.

6 Ethical Aspects

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?

yes

As we deal with patients' personal data we had to get the approval of the Ethics Committee of our institution.

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

Yes

6.1.3 Does the described dataset / output contain personal data?

No

6.1.4 What are the methods used for processing and accessing sensitive/personal information?

Anonymising data where necessary

The data will be collected from consenting patients that will be fully informed that their de-identified and anonymized data may be used for research also after the end of the project. Details about the protocol and the information sheets and consent forms are provided in the Ethics Deliverables. Informed consent for data sharing and long-term preservation should be part of the patients' recruitment and all relevant issues should be clearly explained in the information sheets.

7 Other Issues

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

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